

Linnæus University

Monthly Report December 2025

SENTINEL Wild Birds

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 3 Western Black Sea (Ukraine), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 5 Wadden Sea (the Netherlands), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples from eight nodes, collected from October 2025 to December 2025.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report was published on 24th of November 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17696338>), and as of 15th December 2025, test results have been submitted for 3,897 samples taken from 2,007 individuals representing 33 taxa from eight nodes in and near Europe (Table 1). Of the 3,897 collected samples, 1,625 (42%) were tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 1391 (36%) cloacal swabs, 554 (14%) fecal samples, 269 (7%) feather samples, 56 (1%) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), and 2 (<1%) brain samples.

HPAI detection

Of all samples, 330 (8%) tested positive for avian influenza virus. In total, 23 samples were positive for highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI; H5N1) virus (Figure 1; Table 2). These originated from eight Eurasian Teals in Italy (weeks 48–49; seven juveniles and one second-year bird), three Eurasian Teals in France (week 47; one juvenile and two reported as full-grown), and three Mallards in Sweden (weeks 44–46; all juveniles).

Other subtypes

Subtyped rRT-PCR-positive samples included 37 H5 viruses with undetermined NA subtypes (35 Mallards from Sweden and two Eurasian Teals from France), and one Mallard from Estonia with N1 subtype and undetermined HA subtype. Two Eurasian Teals from Italy were determined as H9N2, and one as H5 together with H12 with undetermined NA subtype (co-infection), all three by Next Generation Sequencing. Many of these positive samples are expected to be fully sequenced, and their results will be included in the next monthly report.

Prevalence and host species sampled

The most sampled species were Eurasian Teal (768 individuals), Mallard (694 individuals), and Barnacle Goose (223 individuals; Table 1). High bird-level prevalence in species with a sample size of at least 80 individuals was found in Mallard (28%), Eurasian Teal (10%), and Dunlin (20%; Table 1). Overall bird-level prevalence was 15% (295 of 2,007 individuals; Table 1).

TABLE 1 Most recently sampled individuals in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of individuals sampled in the wild, number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza virus as well as bird-level prevalence. The table includes previously unpublished samples from October to December 2025.

Group/species	Node 1 Estonia		Node 2 Latvia		Node 2 Sweden		Node 3 Ukraine		Node 4 Georgia		Node 6 Austria		Node 6 Germany		Node 6 Switzerland		Node 7 Italy		Node 8 France		Node 9 Spain		Total			
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Prev.			
<i>Waterfowl</i>																										
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%	
Greater White-fronted Goose	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Taiga Bean Goose	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Barnacle Goose	60	0	0	0	163	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Brent Goose	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	
Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Ruddy Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Duck (unknown species)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9%	
Mallard	3	2	28	4	505	163	20	11	70	9	0	0	4	0	8	0	3	0	51	5	2	0	694	194	28%	
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	15	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18%	
Gadwall	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Northern Pintail	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Northern Shoveler	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Eurasian Wigeon	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0%	
Marbled Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0%	
Eurasian Teal	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	459	42	0	0	0	0	0	0	246	28	59	9	0	0	768	79	10%	
Garganey	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0%	
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0%	
Ferruginous Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	5	0%	
<i>Cormorants</i>																										
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
<i>Storks, Ibises et al.</i>																										
African Sacred Ibis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
<i>Rails</i>																										
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	8	0	0	0	0	59	0	72	0%	
<i>Waders</i>																										
Ruff	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%	
Dunlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	82	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	82	16	20%
Common Redshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0%
Common Greenshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	100%
Numenius sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Common Snipe	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
<i>Larids</i>																										
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
European Herring Gull	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
Total	102	2	29	4	677	166	118	28	546	52	27	1	14	0	42	0	272	28	110	14	70	0	2007	295	15%	

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FIGURE 1 Sample sites in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Sample sites for the 2,007 individuals sampled in Estonia, Latvia, Sweden, Ukraine, Georgia, Austria, Germany, Switzerland, Italy, France, and Spain. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from October to December 2025.

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TABLE 2 Most recently collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus. The table includes previously unpublished samples from October to December 2025.

Group/species	Node 1 Estonia			Node 2 Latvia			Node 2 Sweden			Node 3 Ukraine			Node 4 Georgia			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Germany			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 7 Italy			Node 8 France			Node 9 Spain			Total					
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI						
<i>Waterfowl</i>																																							
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Greater White-fronted Goose	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25	0	0
Taiga Bean Goose	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0
Barnacle Goose	60	0	0	0	0	0	164	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	224	0	0
Brent Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Ruddy Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Duck (unknown species)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	1	0
Mallard	3	2	0	28	4	0	1003	192	4	40	11	0	140	9	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	8	0	0	9	0	0	102	5	0	4	0	0	1341	223	4			
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	30	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	3	0
Gadwall	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Northern Pintail	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0
Northern Shoveler	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
Eurasian Wigeon	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0
Marbled Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Eurasian Teal	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	2	0	0	918	42	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	738	30	14	118	13	5	0	0	0	1782	85	19			
Garganey	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Ferruginous Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																																							
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0
<i>Storks, Ibises et al.</i>																																							
African Sacred Ibis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																																							
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	117	0	0	0	0	0	146	0	0
<i>Waders</i>																																							
Ruff	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0
Dunlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	164	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	164	16	0
Common Redshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0
Common Greenshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0
Numenius sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Common Snipe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Larids</i>																																							
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0
European Herring Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Total	102	2	0	29	4	0	1181	195	4	236	28	0	1092	52	0	27	1	0	14	0	0	42	0	0	815	30	14	220	18	5	139	0	0	3897	330	23			

FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In total, 24,731 samples (negative samples in blue; samples positive for avian influenza virus in orange) have been collected at eight nodes between August 2024 and December 2025, yielding 1,901 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 51 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

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A weekly compilation of all 24,731 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), collected at each node from August 2024 to December 2025, can be seen in Figure 2. Proportion of positive individuals (bird-level prevalence) per week over the total project period, all nodes combined, show one peak in August and one in September 2025, followed by a sustained high proportion of positive individuals since end of October (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Weekly bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Weekly prevalence of individuals positive for avian influenza virus from all nodes combined between August 2024 and December 2025. The figure only includes bird samples (excluding mussels). The number of individuals (here: any individual bird sampled on a given day) are included at the top of the figure.

2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 24th of November 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17696338>), and as of 15th of December 2025, 30 new H5 sequences have been generated from samples positive for avian influenza virus. These samples were all collected from Mallards in Latvia and Sweden (both Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea; N=1 and N=29, respectively), and the sequences were a combination of H5N1 (N=6), H5N3 (N=13), H5N4 (N=7), H5N9 (N=1), and H5 (N=3) subtypes. The three H5 subtype sequences were obtained from two separate samples, where sequences for a number of other subtypes were also obtained (described below). Genetic analysis of the haemagglutinin (HA) gene sequences from these sequences found that the majority (N=24) belonged to the H5 Eurasian avian non-goose Guangdong (EA-nonGsGd) low pathogenicity avian influenza (LPAI)

clade, whilst the remaining sequences (N=6) belonged to the H5 clade 2.3.4.4b of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) (Figure 3A).

The H5 LPAI sequences from Sweden were found to be similar to other H5 LPAI sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project from Sweden (Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea), Estonia (Node 1 Gulf of Finland) and France (Node 8 Camargue Region), as well as other Eurasian LPAI sequences (Figure 3B).

The H5 HPAI sequences from Sweden were determined to be the DI.2.1 sub-genotype of the EA-2024-DI genotype, according to the European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza classification system (<https://github.com/izsvenezie-virology/genin2>). These sequences were obtained from samples collected on separate occasions across a 27-day period (15th October – 11th November 2025) and found to be similar to other H5N1 DI.2.1 sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project from Latvia (also Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea) and Georgia (Node 4 Eastern Black Sea). Additionally, these DI.2.1 sequences collected within the project show similarity to other sequences of the same H5 genotype collected from across Europe and surrounding countries (Figure 3C).

The Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

Aside from the H5 sequences, there have been 51 non-H5 avian influenza sequences generated from samples collected in Austria (Node 6 Lake Constance Region; N=1), Latvia and Sweden (both Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea; N=6 and N=44, respectively). The majority of these samples were collected from Mallards (N=40), but also Black-headed Gulls (N=7), Northern Shovelers (N=3) and an unidentified duck (N=1). The sequence from Austria was of the H9N2 subtype, whilst the sequences from Latvia were of multiple subtypes: 1xH3N2, 2xH3N8, 1xH6N2, 1xH6N6, and 1xH9N2. Of the sequences from Sweden, there were 20 sequences generated from samples containing only one virus and included the following subtypes: 2xH3N8, 1xH4, 3xH4N6, 2xH6N1, 1xH10N2, 2xH11, 1xH13N6, 5xH16N3, 1xN3, and 2xunsubtyped viruses. Additionally, there were seven samples found to contain sequences from multiple subtypes, including the following H-types: 4xH3, 2xH4, 8xH5, 2xH6, 1xH9, 1xH10, 4xH11, and N-types: 2xN1, 1xN2, 5xN3, 4xN4, 3xN6, 3xN8, 4xN9.

This analysis is based on data obtained from the GISAID EpiFlu platform (Elbe and Buckland-Merrett 2017; Shu and McCauley 2017) up to 16th December 2025, and is accessible at <https://doi.org/10.55876/gis8.251217dn>. Where sequences were included that are under a publishing embargo at the time of writing, specific permission to utilise these data was obtained from the Data Provider.

FIGURE 3 Phylogenetic analyses of the H5 HA sequences generated by Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea. **A.** Image of the H5 HA sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project, with the 2.3.4.4b and EA-nonGsGd clades highlighted. **B.** Zoom image of the HA tree focusing on the H5 low pathogenicity avian influenza (LPAI) EA-nonGsGd sequences from Node 1 Gulf of Finland, Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea and Node 8 Camargue Region. The new sequences generated and presented in this report are annotated. **C.** Zoom image of the HA tree focusing on the H5 highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) clade 2.3.4.4b sequences from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea and Node 4 Eastern Black Sea in relation to other sequences from Europe and surrounding countries. The sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project are annotated. In **A** and **B**, tip shapes are coloured according to sampling node, whilst in **C** the tip shapes are coloured according to country of origin.

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3. CONCLUSION

With over 2,000 individual birds representing more than 30 species sampled across eleven countries during the current period, the coverage of active surveillance of wild birds in and near Europe remains substantial.

The current reporting period shows that influenza A virus continues to circulate widely among wild birds in Europe during autumn and early winter. As in previous years, dabbling ducks, such as Mallards and Eurasian Teals, was the ecological group with highest number of detected influenza A virus infections. This in line with the hypothesis of their key role as reservoir hosts for LPAI viruses. Moreover, avian influenza viruses were also detected at a relatively high prevalence (20%) in Dunlins sampled in Ukraine at the end of October. It remains to see whether these findings represent local amplification of duck associated viruses or viruses that spread more efficiently in shorebirds.

H5N1 positive birds were reported from Sweden, France, and Italy, but were restricted to dabbling ducks. All birds were seemingly healthy. In fact, a Mallard from Sweden tested positive for H5N1 on three separate occasions over a short period yet continued to gain weight throughout this time. This suggests that at least some infections, even with H5N1 viruses, may be subclinical in apparently healthy free-living ducks during migration or early winter. Such observations underline the difficulty of detecting early H5N1 spreads based solely on passive surveillance.

The temporal pattern of virus prevalence across all nodes (Figure 3) shows two clear peaks during late summer and autumn, one in early August and another in early September, followed by a sustained period of relatively high prevalence from late October into December. This pattern is consistent with an influx of immunologically naïve juveniles early in the season, followed by extensive congregation of waterbirds at staging and wintering sites later in autumn. The sustained high prevalence into winter emphasizes the importance of continued sampling during this period.

For this report, 30 H5 sequences have been generated, including six from the 2.3.4.4b H5N1 clade. These H5 H5N1 sequences were all of the DI.2.1 sub-genotype, which has predominated in Europe since mid-September 2025 (EFSA *et al.* 2025) and demonstrate high similarity to sequences collected across Europe. This highlights the connectivity between the active sampling being undertaken through the SENTINEL Wild Birds project and other ongoing passive surveillance schemes.

In addition to the H5 sequences, several other subtypes were also detected, including H3, H4, H6, H9, H10, H11, H13, and H16, which further support the data presented in previous SENTINEL Wild Birds reports as to the high subtypic diversity of influenza A viruses circulating in wild birds. A number of these sequences were also identified in samples containing multiple subtypes, indicative of mixed infections within single samples. It is particularly interesting that in six of the seven samples containing multiple subtypes, sequences corresponding to the H5 subtype were identified, including one which was found to belong to the H5 clade 2.3.4.4b of H5N1. Whilst interpretation and understanding mixed infections is complex, these findings further illustrate the potential opportunities for reassortment and genetic diversification of influenza A viruses in wild birds that are presented by the co-circulation of multiple subtypes and pathotypes.

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A large proportion of the positive samples reported here, both HPAI and LPAI, are currently undergoing whole-genome sequencing, and their results will be included in the next monthly report. These analyses are essential for resolving mixed infections, identifying reassortant viruses, and tracing connections between nodes and other European surveillance programs.

Taken together, these results illustrate the ecological and virological complexity of avian influenza circulation during autumn migration. The combination of high subtype diversity, repeated detections in individual birds, and the emergence of HPAI in multiple countries underlines the value of coordinated multi-node surveillance. Integrating genomic results with ecological and temporal information will help us better recognise shifts in virus dynamics and the appearance of new variants

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